

**SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, PARTS OF BIG SCIENCE AND
RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE EUROPEAN MOUNTAIN AREA.
AN ANALYSIS FOR 2008-2018**

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Abstract

The article presents a short analysis for 2008-2018 period regarding Research, professional, technology and administrative activities in some of the European Union mountain area. Presented sectors sustain the big science and research infrastructure in the communitarian space. Research, professional, technology and administrative activities are designed for improving the jobs environment and number, in order to increase the prosperity and quality of life.

Keywords: mountain research, professional, technology and administrative activities; big science

The paper presents a short outlook of the Research, professional, technology and administrative activities in the context of the European Union mountain realities. Although it is a world leader in many areas of technology, the EU is facing a number of challenges the growing challenges posed by traditional competitors and economies alike emerging markets. In key high-tech sectors, European companies have performed poorly in terms of research and development. For example, businesses in the United States of America have invested five times more than European companies competing in semiconductor research and development, four times more in research and development in the software sector and eight times more in biotechnology. (Barladean, 2011)

The EU is one of the most scientifically productive in the world, but it does not contain enough areas of world-class excellence where research generates revolutionary results that can lead to structural change. Main responsibility for building a scientific base competitive public responsibility lies with the member states. It is clear that the EU support can add value, as it has done in the past, through various initiatives that have contributed to the creation of the European Research Area. It is essential to consider how funding provided through the Common Strategic Framework can be used to accelerate progress towards a truly unified ERA.

The EU research and development programs, the introduction of research,

development and innovation policies in Romania, to support and promote cooperation between industrial and service enterprises, universities and research institutes, in order to involve consortia; to stimulate the establishment of interest groups at European level, by focusing on existing competencies at national level, in order to increase their chances of participating in European projects / programs. (Jitaru, 2013)

European policies ”about participation in science and technology underwent three main phases. The initial phase is characterized by the development of a discourse on participation framed as deliberation for science and technology policymaking (2000–2010). The second phase is a transitional phase, integrating the growing emphasis on innovation (2010–2014). The third sees the emergence of a discourse on participation in production of knowledge and innovation (2014-today).” (Macq et al., 2020)

At the EU level, science and research develop considerable frameworks regarding Big Science (are subjects of high organizations/institutions, technologies and politics) and Research Infrastructures. The approach inside the EU frameworks are realized horizontally, having in mind three dimensions: - the intergovernmental cooperation that are established between member states; - Pan-European politics as mentioned in the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) roadmap; – particularized national paths regarding research infrastructure aligned to the

European interest and that receive intensive support from the EU organizations/institutions. The purpose of this complex is science integration, based on “interdependence” and “politicization”. (Ulnicane, 2020)

The science and technology in the EU are connected directly to administrative activities. Interests regarding administrative activities are realities of the contemporary world, but preoccupations exist from long time ago. Throughout the history of civilizations, we can see the existence of the obvious interest of rulers in mastering the sources of knowledge (whether religious, philosophical or scientific) and in monopolizing technologies that translate into resources of social power. However, the phenomenon of political control of knowledge has become more visible and has become a strategic stake in the modern era, to consolidate in the contemporary world, amid the transition to post-industrialism and the so-called information society or knowledge society. The EU has become aware of the need to reorganize its economy, education system and social security, two decades ago, when it found that it had to recover a significant gap with the USA. In the meantime, the Asian science and technology sectors becomes a serious competitor. (Ambrosa, 2010)

Regarding mountain science, technology, professionals and administrative sectors, statistics present continuous positive trends in the last decade.

Thereby, these sectors show means of 35.352,09 (Bulgaria), 393.396,55 (Italia), 52.420,55 (Austria), 47.699,73 (Portugal), 31.647,91 (Romania), 37.100,45 (Slovakia), with standard deviations of 5.661,148 (Bulgaria), 10.014,17 (Italia), 2.063,69 (Austria), 3.614,614 (Portugal), 8.162,452 (Romania), 9.154,217 (Slovakia).

As seen in the following histograms (fig. 1-6), mountain sector regarding science, technology, professionals and administrative activities for Italy and Slovakia presents distribution curves symmetric centered, Portugal with distribution curve positioned on left, and Austria, Bulgaria and Romania with distribution curves oriented on right.

Figure 1. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support activities - Bulgaria

Figure 2. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Italy

Figure 3. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Austria

Figure 4. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Portugal

Figure 5. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Romania

Figure 6. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Slovakia

The first group of countries (Italy and Slovakia) present constant increasing of activities, Portugal a slow decreasing, and the third group of countries (Austria, Bulgaria and Romania) a considerable increasing.

The central trend for this sector in the analyzed period shows that the population of the European mountain economy of the active enterprises in the studied sector increased from 2008 to 2018. In the analyzed period, the intensification of activity was observed. The statistics, presented above, and the histogram confirm the high agglomeration and development trend of this sector in mountain Europe. At the same time, the statistics confirm the intensification of the growth rate of this sector. This sector could be one of the most valuable for mountain Europe.

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